

Synthesis and characterization of some hetero binuclear Ni^{II} Schiff base complexes

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Abstract : Metal complexes of Schiff base ligands derived from *N,N'*-1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldimine) and *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldimine) were used to synthesize a series of hetero binuclear complexes. The general composition of the complexes is $M_aL.M_bL'$, where $M_a = Ni$, $M_b = Rb$ or Cs , $L = N,N'$ -1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldimine) or *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldimine), $L' =$ deprotonated *o*-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 8-hydroxyquinoline. The complexes were characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance measurements, magnetic susceptibility measurements, infrared spectra and UV-Visible spectra. The metal chelate of Schiff base acts as bidentate ligand and coordinates through the phenolic oxygen atoms. The hetero binuclear Schiff base complexes were screened for their antibacterial activity against bacteria *Escherichia coli* MTCC-739, *Staphylococcus aureus* MTCC-96 and for antifungal activity against fungus *Candida albicans* MTCC-227.

Keywords : Schiff base complexes, IR spectra, UV-Visible spectra, antimicrobial activity, MIC.

Introduction

Studies of Schiff bases have attracted the interest of many chemists due to their ability to coordinate with various metal ions^{1,2}. Schiff base ligands and their metal complexes exhibit numerous biological activities such as anti-cancer, antitumor, antibacterial, antifungal, etc.³⁻⁶. This inspires the chemists to synthesize new metal complexes having bioactive properties. In view of this, we report a series of new hetero binuclear Schiff base complexes of the type $M_aL.M_bL'$, where $M_a = Ni$, $M_b = Rb$ or Cs , $L = N,N'$ -1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldimine) or *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldimine), $L' =$ deprotonated *o*-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 8-hydroxyquinoline.

Results and discussion

The physical properties of hetero binuclear complexes of *N,N'*-1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldiminato)nickel(II) [NiES] or *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldiminato)nickel(II) [NiPS] metal chelate with rubidium or cesium metal salts of some organic acids are listed in Table 1. The complexes are generally soluble in methanol, acetone, DMF and DMSO but insoluble in water. The elemental analysis data of the complexes (Table 1) are consistent with the calculated results from the empirical formula of each com-

ound. Molar conductivities of all these complexes were measured in DMSO at 20 (± 0.5) °C and at a concentration of 10^{-3} M. Low value ($0.6-4.2 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) of molar conductivity of the complexes indicate that they are covalent in nature⁷.

Infrared spectra :

NiES, NiPS and their hetero binuclear rubidium and cesium metal complexes exhibit infrared bands in the region $1524-1597 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (Table 2). These bands arise due to phenolic C-O stretching in these compounds⁸. The position of infrared bands near 1530cm^{-1} arising in various transition metal Schiff base complexes has been assigned to phenolic C-O stretching by several authors⁹⁻¹². The mononuclear metal complex, NiES and NiPS exhibits ν_{C-O} str. (phenolic) at 1535 and 1538cm^{-1} respectively which shifts toward higher energy side (with few exceptions) on complexation with rubidium or cesium metal salts of organic acids indicating the participation of oxygen in the C-O-M bond. The major shift of ν_{C-O} str. (phenolic) by 62cm^{-1} in the hetero binuclear complexes certainly indicates the presence of phenoxo bridge. The bands in the far infrared region i.e. $430-493 \text{cm}^{-1}$ and $513-574 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the hetero binuclear complexes are tentatively assigned to M-N str. and M-O str. modes res-

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the hetero binuclear Schiff base complexes

Compd.	Colour	Melt. (m)/Dec. (d)/ Trans. (t) temp. (°C)	Molar cond. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$) mol^{-1})	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Analysis (%) :					Yield (%)
					Found (Calcd.)					
					C	H	N	M _a	M _b	
NiES.RbTNP	Yellow	220m	1.0	2.15	40.72 (41.36)	2.53 (2.50)	10.55 (10.96)	8.84 (9.1)	12.98 (13.39)	60.76
NiES.CsTNP	Pale yellow	230m	0.9	1.95	38.17 (38.50)	2.30 (2.33)	9.92 (10.21)	8.50 (8.56)	18.76 (19.38)	35.28
NiES.RbDNP	Red	200m	0.6	1.88	42.96 (44.50)	2.80 (2.86)	8.92 (9.44)	9.70 (9.89)	14.05 (14.41)	40.54
NiES.Rb1N2N	Light brown	270d	3.3	2.25	51.98 (53.59)	3.38 (3.43)	6.90 (7.21)	9.78 (10.08)	13.92 (14.68)	50.71
NiES.Cs1N2N	Brown	220d	3.1	Dia.	48.20 (49.55)	3.18 (3.17)	6.60 (6.67)	9.20 (9.32)	20.05 (21.11)	20.78
NiES.Cs8HQ	Pale green	200m	3.2	Dia.	48.26 (49.86)	3.34 (3.32)	6.70 (6.98)	9.50 (9.75)	19.55 (22.09)	35.82
NiES.RbONP	Red	230d	1.2	2.20	46.85 (48.16)	3.22 (3.28)	7.54 (7.66)	10.22 (10.70)	15.10 (15.59)	30.51
NiES.CsONP	Brick red	250d	0.7	1.82	43.32 (44.32)	2.95 (3.02)	6.90 (7.05)	9.68 (9.85)	21.62 (22.31)	40.08
NiPS.RbTNP	Yellow	220m	4.2	Dia.	41.86 (42.32)	2.78 (2.76)	10.58 (10.73)	8.66 (8.99)	12.82 (13.10)	70.66
NiPS.CsTNP	Yellow	225m	3.6	Dia.	38.70 (39.45)	2.59 (2.57)	9.78 (10.00)	8.05 (8.38)	18.78 (18.99)	76.05
NiPS.Rb1N2N	Brownish green	240m	0.87	Dia.	54.30 (54.34)	3.68 (3.69)	7.20 (7.04)	9.80 (9.84)	13.75 (14.33)	40.25
NiPS.Cs1N2N	Brown	270d	0.81	Dia.	49.25 (50.34)	3.43 (3.41)	6.48 (6.52)	8.90 (9.11)	19.75 (20.65)	45.19
NiPS.Cs8HQ	Yellowish green	250md	1.2	Dia.	48.86 (45.68)	3.52 (3.57)	6.28 (6.82)	9.50 (9.53)	21.50 (21.59)	38.43
NiPS.Rb8HQ	Yellowish green	200m	0.9	Dia.	54.50 (54.91)	3.88 (3.87)	7.20 (7.39)	9.95 (10.32)	14.85 (15.04)	44.57
NiPS.RbONP	Red	270d	0.88	Dia.	48.35 (49.09)	3.60 (3.55)	7.38 (7.47)	9.90 (10.43)	14.80 (15.20)	35.56

where, m – sharp melting point, d – decomposition temperature and md – melting with decomposition.

pectively¹³. These bands are not present in the uncomplexed ligand, *N,N'*-1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldimine) or *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldimine). In the neutral transition metal chelate, NiES, the bands at 466 and 520 cm^{-1} are assigned to M–N str. and M–O str. respectively while in NiPS, the M–N str. vibration arises at 463, 488 cm^{-1} and M–O str. vibration occurs at 552 cm^{-1} .

UV-Visible spectra :

The electronic absorption bands (Table 2) for the che-

late neutral complexes of Ni^{II} metals of ligand *N,N'*-1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldimine) and *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldimine) observed between 225–316 nm indicates $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition involving molecular orbitals located on the phenolic chromophore and C=N chromophore to the benzene ring. The bands appearing between 395–653 nm in Ni^{II} complexes (i.e. NiES and NiPS) shows charge transfer and *d-d* transition^{12,14}. The absorption maxima of all the hetero binuclear complexes are found in the

Table 2. Spectral data of metal chelates and the hetero binuclear Schiff base complexes

Compd.	Infrared spectra (cm ⁻¹)			UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectra (nm)
	$\nu(\text{C-O})$ phenolic	$\nu(\text{M-O})$	$\nu(\text{M-N})$	
NiES	1535	520	466	225, 314, 398
NiES.RbTNP	1563	522	430	236, 348
NiES.CsTNP	1565	514	430	231, 348
NiES.Cs8HQ	1571	543	492	240, 315, 398, 510
NiES.Rb1N2N	1533, 1597	574, 526	466	243
NiES.Cs1N2N	1536	520	430, 467	240, 341, 394
NiES.RbONP	1540	527	467	225, 244, 253, 314, 398
NiES.CsONP	1536	520	466	225, 239, 258, 284, 334
NiES.RbDNP	1524	515	467	252, 344, 384
NiPS	1538	552	488, 463	239, 316, 395, 653
NiPS.RbTNP	1565	545, 520	453	346, 358, 380, 387, 404
NiPS.CsTNP	1557	513	453	236, 327, 339, 358, 365
NiPS.Rb8HQ	1573	545	493	243, 327, 387
NiPS.Cs8HQ	1573	543	493	238, 327, 389
NiPS.Rb1N2N	1554	520	433	216, 255, 353
NiPS.RbONP	1537	552	463	245, 348, 387
NiPS.CsONP	1534	542	454	232, 348, 382

range 315–510 nm which suggests that there is no changes in stereochemistry of Ni^{II} after adduct formation. The bands of the hetero binuclear complexes in the range 315–510 nm may be attributed to charge transfer whereas bands in the range 216–284 nm is due to intra ligand transition. The absorption bands of medium intensity in NiES and NiPS at 398 and 387 nm respectively indicate square planar geometry¹⁵ of Ni²⁺ with coordination number 4. Similar type of electronic spectral bands are observed in the binuclear complexes of NiES and NiPS with rubidium or cesium metal salts of organic acids suggesting similar square planar geometry of NiES and NiPS in all its binuclear adducts. No absorption bands have been found in the region 700–1200 nm in the hetero binuclear complexes which confirms that the coordination number of Ni²⁺ in the hetero binuclear adducts remains 4 with square planar geometry. The magnetic moment values of most of the hetero binuclear adducts of NiES lies between 1.82–2.25 B.M. which correspond to the presence of one unpaired electron and the square planar geometry¹⁵ with coordination number 4. The magnetic moment value of the hetero binuclear adducts of NiPS is found to be zero

suggesting for their diamagnetic nature. This observation also suggests for their square planar geometry with coordination number 4 for Ni²⁺ ion. For the hetero binuclear adducts of NiES except NiES.Cs1N2N and NiES.Cs8HQ, values of magnetic moment are observed in the range 1.82–2.25 B.M. The deviation from diamagnetism suggests that the hetero binuclear adduct turned into paramagnetic form and may have assumed an octahedral or tetrahedral structure^{16–20}.

The bonding between *N,N'*-1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldiminato)metal(II) complex [M_aES] or *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldiminato)metal(II) complex [M_aPS] and the alkali metal is most likely to occur by dative bonding via two phenolic oxygen atoms of the ligand which has been supported by the IR spectra, magnetic properties and electronic spectral studies of the adducts. The physico-chemical studies as discussed above suggests square planar geometry of M_aES or M_aPS (where M_a = Ni^{II}) with coordination number 4 in all its alkali metal adducts. The probable structure and bonding of the newly prepared compounds with general formula [M_aL.M_bL'] may be shown as in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Probable structure for the hetero binuclear Ni^{II} Schiff base complexes where $M_a = \text{Ni}$, $M_b = \text{Rb}$ or Cs .

Antimicrobial activity :

The *in vitro* antimicrobial screening to the synthesized hetero binuclear complexes were carried out against the bacteria *Escherichia coli* MTCC-739, *Staphylococcus aureus* MTCC-96 and fungi *Candida albicans* MTCC-227. The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) values of the investigated complexes are given in Table 3. The antimicrobial activity of the complexes can be considered on the basis of chelation theory. Chelation causes overlap of the ligand orbital and partial sharing of the positive charge of the metal ion with the donor groups. This reduces the polarity of the metal ion considerably and there is increase in the delocalization of π -electrons over the whole chelate ring. Also, there is enhancement in the penetration through the lipid layers of the cell membrane resulting in interference of the normal cell process of the organisms which restricts further growth of the organisms²¹.

Table 3. Antimicrobial activities (MIC values) of some of the investigated hetero binuclear Schiff base complexes

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
	MTCC-739	MTCC-96	MTCC-227
NiPS.RbONP	200	100	100
NiPS.Rb8HQ	200	200	100
NiPS.Rb1N2N	25	50	50
NiES.CsTNP	200	200	100
NiES.RbONP	200	200	100
NiES.Rb8HQ	100	50	50
NiES.Cs1N2N	100	100	100
NiES.Rb1N2N	25	50	50
Streptomycin	100	25	-
Fluconazole	-	-	100

Experimental

A.R. grade reagents have been used for synthesizing all the complexes. IR spectra were recorded on FTIR spectrophotometer, Shimadzu model 8201 PC in KBr phase. Electronic spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 15 UVB Vis spectrophotometer. Melting point of the compounds was determined on electrical tempo T-1150 melting point apparatus. Molar conductivities were measured with the help of Systronic digital direct conductivity meter-306. Magnetic measurements were carried on Faraday Magnetic Susceptibility balance. Ni^{II} ion has been estimated by complexometric EDTA titrations; estimation of Rb and Cs were done with the help of sodium tetraphenylborate.

Synthetic procedures :

Ni^{II} metal complex of the Schiff base N,N'-1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldimine) :

The Schiff base of *N,N'*-1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldehyde) and 1,2-ethylenediamine in 2 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol for 10 min. The yellow coloured Schiff base was filtered off, washed with ice cold ethanol and dried. A solution of nickel(II) acetate hydrate (2.5 g) in ethanol (15 ml) was added slowly with constant stirring to a hot solution of the Schiff base (ES, 2.81 g). The mixture was further refluxed with constant stirring with the help of magnetic stirrer for 30 min. The solution upon cooling deposited brownish-orange coloured nickel complex. It was filtered off, washed thoroughly with ethanol and dried in electric oven at 80 °C.

Ni^{II} metal complex of the Schiff base N,N'-1,2-propylenebis(salicylalimine) :

The Schiff base of *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylalimine) was prepared by refluxing the salicylaldehyde and 1,2-propylenediamine in 2 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol for 10 min. The yellow coloured Schiff base was filtered off, washed with ice cold ethanol and dried. A solution of nickel(II) acetate hydrate (2.5 g) in ethanol (15 ml) was added slowly with constant stirring to a hot solution of the Schiff base (PS, 2.82 g). The mixture was further refluxed with constant stirring with the help of magnetic stirrer for 30 min. The solution upon cooling deposited brownish-orange coloured nickel complex. It was filtered off, washed thoroughly with ethanol and dried in electric oven at 80 °C.

Hetero binuclear complexes constituting Ni^{II} metal ion and rubidium or cesium metal :

N,N'-1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaliminato)nickel(II) [NiES] or *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaliminato)nickel(II) [NiPS] was taken in absolute alcohol in a conical flask and rubidium or cesium metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol or 8-hydroxyquinoline were added to it in 1 : 1 molar proportion. The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate at 75–80 °C with constant stirring for 40 min. The characteristic coloured adducts were precipitated in hot condition which was filtered, washed thoroughly with absolute ethanol and dried in an electric oven at 80 °C.

Antimicrobial activity :

The hetero binuclear complexes have been tested for *in vitro* growth inhibitory activity against the bacteria *Escherichia coli* MTCC-739, *Staphylococcus aureus* MTCC-96 and fungi *Candida albicans* MTCC-227 by microplate method of Eloff²² using broth nutrient as the medium. Different dilution of chemical were prepared in DMSO solvent and added to the well. The microplates were incubated at 37 (±1) °C and examined after 12 h and reabsorbed after 48 h. After 48 h, each was screened and lowest dilution of the chemical without any growth of the organism was recorded as MIC. These test organisms were also checked with some antibiotics like streptomycin and antifungal like fluconazole.

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